

NARENDRA MODI

Prime Minister of India

सत्यमेव जयते

Welcome : Sardar Dilbag Singh Khalsa

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Grievance Details

Registration Number

PMOPG/E/2025/0109995

Name

Sardar Dilbag Singh Khalsa

Date of receipt

30/07/2025

Address

Mehtanagar Pandit deendayal upadhyay ward mehtanagar
Pandit deendayal upadhyay ward mehtanagar

State

Chhattisgarh

District

Balodabazar-Bhatapara

Mobile Number

9981240811

Email ID

sdskdilbag1994@gmail.com

Phone Number

Not Provided

Grievance Description

Health & Family Welfare >> Policy Matters >> Mental Healthcare Act 2017

In IIT Bhubaneswar we have a startup named Edrive , they called me when it was heavy rain , I got hit by dominos female gig worker, I got injured, dominos use azimoto and lots of harmful chemicals, kindly cancel the licence of both the startup, their gig worked are paid less so they are frustrated, and just do aggumet who pays all taxes on time fine them 1000 crore and cancel the licence, kindly provide me CCTV surveillance and all footage of All the IIT , NIT all the institute of India and as they are responsible citizens and using drugs and alcohol in the campus

Communication Details

Sn.	Date of Action	Action	From	To
1	30/07/2025	RECEIVED THE GRIEVANCE	You	Prime Minister's Office
2	31/07/2025	REMINDER RECEIVED FROM COMPLAINANT	You	Department of Health & Family Welfare
3	31/07/2025	REMINDER RECEIVED FROM COMPLAINANT	You	Department of Health & Family Welfare
4	07/08/2025	REMINDER RECEIVED FROM COMPLAINANT	You	Department of Health & Family Welfare

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